

Asaf Ibrahimian is Chief Operating Officer and Director of Business Affairs at RDM Capital Funding, a New Jersey based alternative lending company that provides capital to small businesses, who either have been turned away from traditional lenders, or don't want to go through the headache of submitting countless documents only to be rewarded with months of waiting.

Before joining RDM Capital Funding in 2015, Asaf Ibrahimian served as Director of Operations at R&A Consulting Group Inc since September 2012. In this position, he oversaw all day to day operations, developed sales training methods and instituted company practice in order to maximize revenues. Prior to R&A Consulting Group Inc, Asaf Ibrahimian served for over two years as Director of Business Development at Strikly Kosher Inc. Here he managed 8 refreshment stands at MetLife Stadium and Yankee Stadium with sales of approximately \$3000 per stand per game. His responsibilities included supervising employees, preparing and distributing employees' work schedules, implementing efficient procedures for stocking, cooking and selling merchandise to maximize productivity, while monitoring and maintaining appropriate inventory levels to meet demand. He was also in charge of hiring and training new employees on specific functions and policies and ensuring prompt and accurate processing of each customer order to maintain reputation of superior service, resulting in high level of repeat customers and referrals.

As a graduate of the Fairleigh Dickinson University, Asaf Ibrahimian holds a Bachelor's Degree of business administration.

Results-driven business professional equipped with leadership and management experience in Mortgage Banking. Enthusiastic problem solver with business acumen at creating and managing high-performing, cross-functional teams and continuously improving processes and procedures. Leader with an effective combination of strengths in large-scale national operations, strategic planning and succession planning with outstanding communication skills and the ability to mentor future leaders.

Asaf Ibrahimian has a great deal of experience in developing process efficiencies in an organization. He finds areas for potential cost savings while keeping customer service levels and loan quality high. He has years of leadership and management experience in the mortgage industry, including expertise in credit risk, underwriting, operations, regulatory compliance, post-closing, policies and procedures, and project management. He also poses outstanding communication skills and the ability to identify future leaders.